

Generative artificial intelligence and ethics: University faculty, staff, and students' views

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Abstract

This exploratory study examines the ethical viewpoints, and perspectives of faculty, staff, and students concerning Generative Artificial Intelligence (GAI) technology tools at a mid-Atlantic university as of August 2023. This qualitative study is guided by Diffusion of Innovation Theory, and the Eight Key Questions Ethical Reasoning Framework, and aims to document the early reactions of the academic community to GAI's introduction into educational contexts. A university wide survey was distributed to document the perceptions, concerns, and expectations of the academic community with respect to GAI as it emerged. The results indicated a range of responses to GAI from optimism that GAI could be used to augment teaching and provide additional support to students, to concern over issues such as academic honesty, bias, privacy of data, and devaluation of authentic learning experiences. The study indicates the complexity of incorporating GAI into higher education. The study establishes a foundation for future studies on the sociotechnical implications of GAI, and includes a University GAI Ethics Guidance Checklist to assist in the ethical implementation of GAI.

Keywords: *Generative Artificial Intelligence; Ethical Considerations; Higher Education; Diffusion of Innovation; Institutional Policy*

JEL Classification: I23; I28; O33; D83; A13

1. Introduction

There is a growing and rapid evolution of Generative Artificial Intelligence (GAI) tools such as ChatGPT creating a major transition in Higher Education. At the time this research was conducted in the Spring of 2023, virtually all educators of higher education were just becoming aware of the magnitude of the disruption that GAI tools are causing. The emergence of tools like ChatGPT has caused a level of disruption and uncertainty previously unknown to the field of higher education in terms of its educational practice, ethics and assessment (Cotton et al., 2023; Adel et al., 2024; Memarian & Doleck, 2023; Mamo et al., 2024). Through the application of Rogers' (2003) Diffusion of Innovations (DoI) Theory, which provides an explanation for how new technologies and educational innovations are disseminated throughout a social system, we explored how an academic community initially perceived and evaluated GAI at the inception of its adoption within an academic community. Likewise, central to this work is the Eight Key Questions (8KQs) Framework (James Madison University, 2018), a set of guiding questions that are intended to facilitate the process of ethical thinking and decision-making. Both of these frameworks provide the conceptual lens through which to understand both how GAI diffuses throughout an academic community and how faculty, staff and students think about the ethical implications of using GAI. However, the extant literature primarily addresses issues related to academic integrity, the application of GAI in classrooms, or general debates regarding ethics (Selwyn, 2024; Adel et al., 2024; Mamo et al., 2024), and there is limited empirical research regarding how entire university communities interpret and respond to the early stages of institutional GAI adoption. Furthermore, few studies explore how the use of ethical reasoning frameworks guide the early sense making processes of university communities.

Consequently, this study sought to accomplish two purposes: (1) to describe the perceptions and ethical considerations of GAI among faculty, staff and students during the early stages of its adoption; and (2) to explore how DoI and the 8KQs together reveal patterns of developing ethical reasoning during the initial stages of GAI adoption.

Scholarship on GAI in higher education has generally addressed issues of academic integrity, instructional strategies, and evolving policy direction and therefore, there has been very little empirical investigation of how various constituencies of a university as a whole interpret and make sense of GAI during its first phase of diffusion. By documenting the development of ethical reasoning prior to the establishment of institutional norms and policies, this study provides a rare moment-in-time look at how social-technical judgments evolve simultaneously with diffusion processes in real time. This early evidence will serve as a foundation for understanding how higher education communities assess the risks and benefits, and responsibilities associated with GAI during a period of institutional uncertainty.

The setting for this research emerged in August 2023, when the authors' university had provided no formal guidance on the use of GAI. On August 15, 2023, in a campus-wide email, the provost stated that the institution would "collaboratively and deliberatively...assess the landscape and develop local policies and common language on the use of GAI" (H. Coltman, personal communication, August 15, 2023). Prior to the development of such policies, students were informed that their use of GAI would be governed by each professor's determination of what constituted acceptable use. This lack of institutional guidance reflects a larger national and international trend, where institutions of higher education were struggling to determine how to create such policies, how to support faculty in developing appropriate uses of GAI, and how to assess potential risks associated with GAI (Memarian & Doleck, 2023; Adel et al., 2024).

As a result of the lack of institutional guidance, an interdisciplinary working group of researchers from the College of Education at James Madison University was established to investigate the implications of GAI for teaching and learning. The working group launched a university-wide qualitative survey of faculty, staff, and students to inquire: What ethical considerations influence the use of GAI for teaching and learning? This study fills a critical gap in the emergent literature on GAI in higher education by providing empirical data on how a university community makes ethical decisions during the early stages of GAI adoption, a perspective that is infrequently documented in the existing literature (Mamo et al., 2024; Selwyn, 2024). This manuscript presents qualitative results from that survey and examines how DoI and the 8KQs framework together can explain the early stages of GAI adoption and the ethical reasoning processes of a university community navigating a rapidly changing technology environment.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Generative artificial intelligence

The term generative artificial intelligence (GAI) applies to the new generation of artificial intelligence systems that produce output that is similar to creative work done by humans (i.e. images, videos, music, text, etc.). The AI's ability to learn, especially through deep learning, enables it to learn from data sets to recognize patterns and structure of those works and then to produce new works based on what it learned. Although the output produced by GAI does not result from personal preference or opinion like human-created output does, the output of a GAI system is influenced by the quality and diversity of the training data set as well as the refinement of the models used in developing the GAI (Farrelly & Baker, 2023).

A number of tools, using AI, have recently become available that can produce digital artwork and graphics, music composition, image identification and description, and even video content creation/summary. The emergence of these tools has caused both excitement and concern among academics regarding the influence of GAI on the creation of knowledge, the nature of academic work, and the legitimacy of academic endeavors (Farrelly & Baker, 2023).

Research has recently been initiated to investigate the ethical implications of widespread adoption of GAI in higher education. For example, Mogavia and colleagues (2024) surveyed social media posts of early adopters across higher education, K–12 education, and vocational skills training to determine the most common themes in their postings. Their results indicated that the primary areas of concern posted by the users included productivity, efficiency, and ethics. They concluded that GAI could increase accessibility to education but may also be detrimental to the development of original thinking and creativity. This study extends the research of Mogavia and colleagues (2024) by examining how faculty members, staff, and students perceive the ethical implications of GAI usage in higher education.

Simultaneously, there is increasing evidence in the literature regarding more formalized and systemic approaches to AI ethics. Specifically, Schlagwein and Willcocks (2023) identified the three central challenges in the governance of GAI: fairness, accountability, and transparency. Larson et al. (2024) investigated the tension between rapid innovation and institutional oversight, demonstrating that many universities fall behind in developing policies that protect integrity while allowing responsible experimentation. In addition, prior to the advent of GAI, Jobin et al. (2019) developed an AI ethics framework consisting of core principles (fairness, responsibility, transparency, privacy, and non-maleficence) and supporting principles (trust, beneficence, solidarity, sustainability, freedom, and dignity) that is commonly used in Information Systems literature. After conducting an extensive review of the emergent research on ethics and GAI, Laine et al., (2025) developed new GAI ethics principles (intellectual property, robustness, sociocultural responsibility, truthfulness, recognition of malicious uses, and human-centric design) that address specific and nuanced ethical concerns that were not previously considered. Additionally, Laine et al. (2025) proposed a framework for integrating ethical GAI into educational settings that emphasizes inclusivity, equity, and responsible innovation. The more recent developments in the area of GAI ethics expand the scope of the ethical discussion beyond academic integrity to include structural issues such as bias in training data, disparities of power between technology developers and users, and the broader societal obligations of educational institutions.

Placing this examination of early user perceptions within a framework that is more fully developed allows for clarification of how initial reactions to GAI supported and deviated from an established AI ethics framework (Jobin et al., 2019) and a current GAI ethics framework (Laine et al., 2025). A void identified by researchers in the latter framework and filled by this study is the need for end-users' ethical considerations in their experiences with GAI. The findings of this study represent a point in time when institutional policies did not exist and the discourse of ethics surrounding GAI was still developing. The inclusion of end-user perspectives in extending these frameworks provides a greater depth of understanding of how ethical concerns arise in the context of everyday practice, rather than in abstract policy formulations. By illustrating how faculty, staff, and students assessed fairness, responsibility, and potential harms associated with GAI as it initially entered higher education, this study contributes empirical grounding that will complement and strengthen the conceptual GAI ethics frameworks being developed.

2.2 Faculty and staff use of GAI in higher education

GAI offers tremendous potential to improve how teachers teach, how students learn, how researchers conduct research, and how administrators run day-to-day operations in U.S. colleges and universities. Almost half of U.S. education leaders recognize "the GAI's potential to enhance the capacity of their institutions" (Inside Higher Education & Hanover Research, 2024, p. 14).

Higher Education uses GAI in the administration and operations of higher education institutions: Chatbots and Intelligent Assistants answer students', faculty, and staff questions; they schedule appointments; and they complete routine tasks (Labadze et al., 2023). Additionally, GAI has been applied to enhance campus operations by optimizing facilities management, energy use, transportation and budget/finance through data analysis and recommendations for

efficiency (Yaiprasert & Hidayanto, 2024). Examples of emerging applications of GAI in Higher Education include enrollment management, student advising, academic planning, and alumni relations.

While GAI is being utilized by faculty to assist with developing instructionally relevant materials, providing feedback on students' writing, grading assessments, etc., there are still a lot of questions regarding the development of appropriate use policies (McDonald et al., 2025). As well, AI is being utilized to utilize automated grading of student written assignments (Mizumoto & Eguchi, 2023).

Despite the numerous benefits of GAI, many leaders within Higher Education have expressed concerns regarding the risks associated with academic integrity: 73% of Provosts from universities stated that they were concerned about the possibility that GAI could negatively impact academic honesty (Inside Higher Education & Hanover Research, 2024, p. 14). Wiley (2024) conducted a survey of 850 college instructors and 2067 students in North America, and reported that students indicated a rate of utilization of GAI tools was three times that of instructors (45% vs. 15%) and that instructors reported a high level of concern relative to the accuracy of GAI, and that GAI may be detrimental to critical thinking, skills-based learning, and cheating.

2.3 Student use of GAI in higher education

The rapid emergence of GAI-based technologies also fundamentally changes the student experience. A primary application of this technology is to assist students with writing and completing homework assignments. In this capacity, large language models (LLM) such as ChatGPT can be used to create drafts of written work, evaluate and provide feedback on written work, detect plagiarism, and suggest ways to enhance the quality of written work (Cotton et al., 2023). While there are legitimate concerns regarding the use of these tools to facilitate dishonesty in academic writing, there is evidence to support the notion that most students view these tools as supplemental aids, similar to spell-checking or citation generation software (Putra, 2023). As researchers continue to investigate the use of GAI, institutions will likely evolve their policies to reflect the changing nature of teaching and learning.

In addition to supporting writing and assignment completion, GAI is being used by students for a variety of other purposes including programming, quantitative analysis, research synthesis, multimedia creation, and time management (George & Wooden, 2023). At the graduate level, GAI is increasingly being employed at each stage of the research cycle, from the initial search of the literature and the analysis of data to the construction of a model and the drafting of a research paper (Ray, 2023). While some of the uses of GAI may seem obvious (e.g. using a calculator to perform mathematical computations), its increasing role as a tool to support learning and studying is less well understood. For instance, intelligent tutoring systems, which utilize AI, provide students with personalized learning paths and practice opportunities (Bhutoria, 2022); while AI chatbots and virtual assistants assist students in finding resources, answering questions, and augmenting human tutoring and advising (Essel et al., 2022).

A number of researchers have explored student attitudes toward GAI. In a study of 500 university students in the Philippines, Obenza et al. (2024) found that students perceived ChatGPT as easy to use, effective, and useful for their learning. Students expressed satisfaction with ChatGPT and indicated a willingness to use the platform for learning. Although students expressed moderate concern regarding the implications of GAI on the value of education, social learning, and the development of students' proficiency in the English language, students were also concerned regarding inaccuracies, plagiarism, and the potential negative effect of GAI on students' self-reliance and critical thinking skills. Similar to Laine et al.'s (2025) recommendation that scholars conduct research on "end-users' views of the ethics of GenAI," our study extends Obenza et al.'s (2024) study by examining how students, faculty, and staff discuss the ethical implications of GAI in the context of higher education.

While there is a growing body of literature focused on the development of GAI tools, the adoption of these tools by faculty, the use of GAI by students, and the development of AI ethical frameworks, the extant literature does not

examine how the collective community of higher education develops ethical rationales in response to the introduction of GAI into academic environments, particularly in the absence of formal institutional policies. Thus, the existing literature focuses primarily on conceptual frameworks (Jobin et al., 2019; Laine et al., 2025) or on the behavior of individual users (Obenza et al., 2024; Wiley, 2024), but leaves unexamined how faculty, staff, and students develop assessments of fairness, accountability, and harm as GAI becomes integrated into academic life. Therefore, the present study addresses this gap by conducting empirical research that explores the intersection of ethical frameworks and technology adoption, and examines end users' developing real-time ethical rationales in response to the transition of GAI into their institutions.

2.4 Diffusion of innovations and technology adoption in higher education

Theory on the diffusion of innovation (DoI) has been widely utilized to describe the manner in which technological innovations diffuse through an institution, including the extent to which certain innovations can be adopted by the majority of an institution's constituents while other innovations can only be adopted by a minority of early adopters (Rogers, 2003). There have been numerous studies that have applied DoI to understand the manner in which faculty in higher education settings adopt various forms of technology, including learning management systems (Porter & Graham, 2016), teaching online (Borrego & Henderson, 2014), mobile technologies (Kirkwood & Price, 2014), and information system innovations (Hardgrave et al., 2003). Studies using DoI in higher education contexts have demonstrated that the rate at which a particular type of technology is adopted depends upon whether the user believes it will provide a relative advantage over traditional methods, if it fits with the user's existing instructional norms, the institutional culture of the setting, and the availability of professional support.

The research also indicates that early adopters play an important role in shaping the diffusion pattern of technologies. Early adopters frequently assist their peers in experimenting with new technologies, are involved in informal networks that facilitate peer-to-peer learning, and legitimize the use of new technologies within an academic unit (Borrego & Henderson, 2014; Porter & Graham, 2016). In the case of GAI, these dynamics are particularly pertinent since the rapid and policy-free environment in which initial adoption took place presents similar characteristics to those described above.

Critics of DoI have stated that the theory portrays diffusion as a linear process and does not adequately account for the many complex factors that affect the adoption of a new technology, including ethical, political, and social considerations. Critics contend that DoI fails to address issues such as power inequities, institutional risk, the vulnerability of stakeholders, and the ethical implications of adoption decisions (Moore & Ellsworth, 2014; Straub, 2009). The critique is particularly applicable to GAI, where fairness, authorship, data privacy, bias, and academic integrity are among the concerns that influence the decision to use GAI, in addition to perceptions of usefulness and ease of use.

While DoI provides a useful conceptualization of how an innovation spreads, there are no previous studies that examine the relationship between the way an innovation diffuses and the ethical reasoning of the users of the innovation, especially during the early stages of the diffusion when there is little to no formal institutional policy regarding the use of the innovation. Since GAI was introduced to academia in a decentralized, rapid, and policy-free environment, ethical uncertainty became entwined with the decisions to adopt GAI. In such environments, the perceptions of fairness, accountability and the potential for harm associated with the use of GAI may become just as significant in determining adoption as the perceived usefulness and ease of use of GAI. This study addresses this void by combining DoI with the Eight Key Questions (8 KQs) ethical reasoning framework, allowing for the analysis of how participants simultaneously evaluated the practical and ethical implications of GAI during the earliest phases of its diffusion.

3. Conceptual framework

3.1 Diffusion of innovation

The Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) Theory provides an explanation for how communications flow about new ideas through channels of communication over time in a social system (Rogers, 1995, 2003). By building on prior DOI research in higher education, Hardgrave et al. (2003); Porter & Graham (2016); Borrego & Henderson (2014), our application of the DOI Framework helps us to better understand how GAI rapidly diffused throughout the university community. The DOI Framework identifies several key attributes of innovations that affect adoption rates. Specifically, the DOI Framework attributes include Relative Advantage, Compatibility, Complexity, Observability, and Trialability. Of these attributes, Trialability is particularly applicable to GAI as it was free to use, and therefore all members of the university community were able to experience the trial version of GAI without fear of institutional policy ramifications.

However, the DOI Framework does not provide sufficient insight into the ethical uncertainty associated with the adoption of GAI. Research has shown that the DOI Framework may be limited in its ability to address issues related to ethics, power dynamics and institutional responsibility (Moore & Ellsworth, 2014; Straub, 2009). In order to address this limitation, our study utilizes the DOI Framework in conjunction with a structured ethical decision-making model, the Eight Key Questions (8KQs), to assess the ethical implications of the adoption of GAI from the perspectives of faculty, staff, and students.

3.2 Eight key questions: Ethical reasoning in action

Table 1. The eight key questions (8KQs)

Ethical principal	Question
Fairness	How can I (we) act justly, equitably, and balance legitimate interests?
Outcomes	What actions achieve the best short- and long-term outcomes for me and all others?
Responsibilities	What duties and/or obligations apply?
Character	What actions help me (us) become my (our) ideal self (selves)?
Liberty	How do I (we) show respect for personal freedom, autonomy, and consent?
Empathy	How would I (we) act if I (we) cared deeply about everyone involved?
Authority	What do legitimate authorities (e.g., experts, law, my religion/god(s)) expect?
Rights	What rights, if any, (e.g., innate, legal, social) apply?

4. Synthesis and research question

Taken as a whole, the literature demonstrates that although faculty, staff, and students in higher education adopted GAI relatively quickly, their early reactions to GAI were influenced by a lack of direction on what was appropriate and evolving norms around ethics. The contemporary AI ethics standards (Larson et al., 2024; Schlagwein & Willcocks, 2023; Laine et al., 2025) which currently advocate for fairness, accountability, transparency, inclusive and proactive governance, had not evolved sufficiently to guide our participants' decisions. In addition to providing a means to examine the early perceptions of participants using a framework established at a much later date than when we gathered our data, this study helps to identify how initial gaps in making ethical decisions may have either led to current "best practice" or diverge from them. As such, the research question that guided this study is based upon this synthesized literature and is as follows: How do the ethical concerns associated with the adoption of Generative AI for instructional purposes influence the choices of faculty, staff, and students within institutions of higher education? By studying this at a point

in time when there was little institutional guidance on the use of GAI, this study presents an essential first look at the ways in which faculty and student decisions regarding the adoption of GAI are ethically reasoned, and are therefore the earliest form of evidence documenting how ethical concerns change over time and provide a base line for developing future policies and training programs for faculty and staff.

5. Methods

5.1 Data sources

Data collection for the survey was approved by the university review board. To establish content validity, the survey was developed and refined by the team of researchers with expertise across content areas, including technology education, literacy education, science education, social justice education, and multiple levels of teacher education. The survey included Likert-scale responses about perceptions and uses of GAI in addition to open-response items. This study shares findings from qualitative analysis of an open-ended question regarding GAI and ethics.

The survey was electronically mailed via university distribution lists in August 2023, before the academic school year started. A total of 362 participants (228 students, 91 faculty, 43 staff) submitted to the survey with at least one usable response. Because the analysis reported here focused on a single open-ended item designed to elicit participants' perceptions and reasoning, we excluded blank and "N/A" responses to that question. This process yielded an analytic sample of 256 respondents (156 students, 70 faculty, and 30 staff) whose qualitative responses formed the basis for the analysis. There was representation from nine different colleges across campus (Table 2). The vast majority of the participants (80%) reported being somewhat or very familiar with GAI (Table 3).

Table 2. College of respondents

College	Faculty	Staff	Students
Arts and Letters	17	4	29
Business	7	3	25
Education	15	5	10
Health and Behavioral Sciences	11	2	26
Integrated Science and Engineering	6	1	22
Science and Mathematics	7	0	18
Visual and Performing Arts	5	1	9
Professional and Continuing Education	2	0	6
Graduate School	0	0	11
No College listed	2	14	0

Note: Some faculty and staff are associated with multiple colleges.

Table 3: GAI familiarity among respondents

Familiarity Level	Faculty	Staff	Students
Very Familiar	20	8	58
Somewhat Familiar	37	12	71
Somewhat Unfamiliar	8	3	14
Very Unfamiliar	5	7	13

5.2 Qualitative data analysis

Our data analysis process was iterative (Merriam, 1998). Our first pass through the data looked broadly across the survey items to understand our sample, comparing responses on survey items about familiarity and use of GAI among subgroups of students, faculty, and staff. Next, after narrowing our research question for the current analysis, we looked closely at responses to a single open response survey item (See full question text in Appendix A.). This question, the first long-format open response question in the survey, provided some background related to GAI and then asked respondents to share their thoughts on the ethical considerations for use of this tool for “teaching and learning” (faculty/staff) or “learning” (students).

We engaged in several cycles of qualitative coding to generate themes and assertions from the data (Saldaña, 2016). First, we printed all 277 non-blank responses to this question and gathered five members of the research team to engage in a variation of “cutting and sorting” responses into piles (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). We first split responses into fine-grain categories before lumping related categories together (Ryan & Bernard, 2003). Through this variation on open coding, we generated a first round of potential codes for the data. These codes were “...word[s] or short phrases that symbolically assign a summative, salient, essence-capturing, and/or evocative attribute for a portion of [our] language-based data” (Saldaña, 2016, p. 4).

Next, two of the faculty researchers and a graduate student assistant consolidated these codes, developed a codebook, and systematically applied the codes to each survey response. To attend to reliability, we first coded together, then coded a subset separately and compared our code applications, with multiple meetings for consensus building. In total, 102 responses (37%) of survey response were double- or triple-coded, with an overall agreement on code application of 90%. Codes and counts of code applications are available in Table 4.

Finally, our research group met over several occasions to generate themes (Gibson & Brown, 2009; Saldaña, 2016). We consolidated codes and drafted and revised overarching ethical questions that summarize the broad themes of the analysis.

A distinguishing feature of this study is its timing: data were collected before institutional policies or norms regarding GAI had been established. This provided a unique methodological window into early diffusion, allowing us to capture participants’ ethical reasoning at a moment when perceptions were still forming and guidance was minimal. Because the open-response question (Appendix A) directly invited participants to articulate ethical considerations, the resulting dataset offers an unusually rich view of how end users make sense of both the promise and risks of GAI during a formative stage of adoption.

6. Findings and discussion

From our iterative analysis, we generated overarching themes related to our research question about faculty, staff, and students’ views on the ethical considerations of GAI in higher education. In line with our conceptual framework, we offer these themes as considerations that other universities might use in the formulation of policies and conduct related to the use of GAI in teaching and learning. Elements of the Eight Key Questions (James Madison University [JMU], 2018) are italicized throughout. Table 5 situates our findings alongside the 8 KQs and established core AI ethical principles (Jobin et al., 2019) while Table 6 situates our findings alongside the 8 KQs and the new GAI principles drawn from Laine and colleagues’ (2025) systematic review of emerging GAI literature. Importantly, there is nuanced overlap of findings within and across new and established ethical principles as well as contradictions (Laine et al., 2025).

Table 4. Codebook and count of code applications

Codes	Code description	#
Teaching / learning	Participant describes a specific application for teaching or learning. Use when there is a reference to course assignments, implications for learning, considerations about teaching, etc.	141
Concerns about plagiarism/cheating / AI detection	Participant describes issues with using GAI to generate work on assignments and attributing it as their own efforts. May describe issues with trying to detect GAI and the inaccuracies that occur. May worry about students cheating themselves out of learning.	85
Depends on use	Participant may mention strengths and problems, but the response is fairly balanced. Would also apply this code if participant discusses how it depends on the way the user is using GAI.	67
Concerns about accuracy / bias	Participant describes inaccurate information or bias perpetuated by GAI based on training data.	47
Have not used	Response states that they have not personally used GAI	43
"Need to figure it out"	Participant describes how instructors, the university, or society need to take steps to determine how/why it will be used/how it will work.	33
General positive	Clearly states a positive view of the technology in relation to teaching and learning, uses strong positive language.	31
Concerns about ownership / privacy	Participant describes concerns related to use of others' intellectual property or the information that chatbots collect from the user. Do not code for this if worry is about student ownership of their classwork.	28
General negative	Clearly states a negative view of the use of this technology in teaching and learning, uses strong negative language.	26
Not worried	Comparable to existing technology, it expresses doubt about what GAI is capable of, does not see connection to teaching and learning in their subject area in a way that would create ethical issues.	16
Research	Participant mentions use of GAI in the context of scholarly work, publications, or research	9
Unsure	Participant expresses not being sure what they think about the technology	8

Note: Multiple codes could be applied to the same response. For example, 17 respondents who indicated they had not used GAI still weighed in with their perspective and had additional codes applied to their response.

Our survey provides an instructive snapshot of the ethical considerations weighing on students, faculty, and staff as the technology in question was beginning to cross the “chasm” of DoI. Even as our analysis continued alongside the technology changing rapidly, these overarching themes continued to ring true and complement the extant literature on usage (e.g., Cotton et al., 2023) and ethical considerations for GAI (e.g., McDonald et al., 2025; Laine et al., 2025). What distinguishes this study from prior research is its multi-role perspective, which reveals how students, faculty, and staff converge and diverge in their ethical judgments. By integrating these perspectives, the study advances the field’s understanding of institution-wide sensemaking and demonstrates how ethical reasoning is distributed across constituent groups during early GAI adoption.

6.1 Ethical consideration #1: Assessing impact of GAI on student outcomes

A central purpose of higher education is student learning. Therefore, a key ethical question regarding GAI in this context is whether and the extent to which it supports the outcome of student learning. When our survey was administered, there was limited causal evidence available regarding this question. Consistent with Bhutoria (2022) and Essel et al. (2022), survey respondents across groups did indicate perceptions that GAI tools have potential to enhance teaching and learning. However, other students wrote from first-hand experience, and some characterized the potential for learning with GAI in a positive light: “It can provide useful information on conceptual topics, and the quickness with which it provides responses makes it seem as if it’s a conversation with the real person, so it helps in our absorption and in retaining of information.”

Conversely, a number of participants expressed fear that GAI might hinder learning, including slowing the development of critical thinking and writing skills. A student worried: “It can and will absolutely ruin how people will learn. It scares me to think how people will use this to get ahead in school while having zero hard or soft skills picked up in the process.” A faculty member echoed this view: “If GAI can replace these skills for [students], then they are leaving here with no valid marketable skills of their own.” These distinct perspectives underscore the need to gather and assess ongoing data about student learning outcomes following use of GAI.

6.1.1 Determining how to address inaccuracy and bias

The data was full of examples of participants detailing the harm from bias inherent in the training of the LLM and the impacts that would have on teaching, learning, politics, and students’ future success and abilities. One student explained, “It learns from things humans have written, and therefore inherits the same biases that humans have. It is a mistake to think of an AI as an objective and impartial robot; it can enforce systems of oppression built into society.” Other faculty described the need for students to have the necessary content and skills to use GAI effectively and notice mistakes it makes. The harm resulting from misinformation has profound outcomes and implications for our political elections, K-16 education, and our students’ skills needed for the careers we are preparing them for at our institution. Clear concerns throughout the data centered on the erosion of students’ critical thinking, soft and hard skills, and written communication.

6.2 Ethical consideration #2: Understanding perceptions of fairness

A prominent ethical consideration for both students and faculty/staff respondents was fairness. This includes concerns over fairness related to whether students would have equitable access to learning experiences and outcomes, as well as concerns that might be more accurately described as contemplating justness. Both students and faculty wondered about the implications of GAI for classroom assessment: Is it fair if some students use GAI to produce or support their production of class assignments and others do not?

Most students took the stance that using GAI on assignments is unjust. A student wrote: "Students using GAI to create papers or responses to assignments and receiving credit for that is wildly unfair to students who do their work." This shows attention to procedural fairness – the expectation that equal cases be treated equally. It also implies the mutual exclusivity of using GAI and "doing the work," a common framing among student participants.

At the time the GAI survey was distributed, the GAI diffusion process was still in its early stages; therefore, the "work" involved in developing techniques such as prompt engineering and how to generate high-quality GAI outputs had just begun, and the "work" of using the technology effectively (and/or ethically), was not very evident in the responses. The students varied in determining where to "draw the line," with some students indicating that any use of GAI would be unethical, while others indicated that using GAI as a "tool for generating ideas", "brainstorming," or "simplifying/shortening the time to complete the assignment" could be acceptable as long as "you don't plagiarize GAI ideas word-for-word." One student took the lens of evaluating the role of faculty/staff and student and said, "Just like students can't plagiarize their assignments and must submit their own original work, so too should faculty and staff adhere to the same standard by creating their own original lecture materials, presentations, slide shows, etc." This student's comment raises significant questions concerning the ethical obligation of faculty and students, and indicates that 'just' educational practices should promote reciprocal expectations of honesty and accountability among all participants.

6.2.1. GAI, inclusion, and equity

Several participants recognized the usefulness of GAI as an accessibility tool for students with disabilities or for those whom English is their second language. For example, "These tools could be useful for students with disabilities who need help organizing their thoughts on large amounts of information." Conversely, another student considered the harmful and inequitable outcomes of using GAI. "I know some of my peers are entirely unwilling to use it, and I would feel bad for using that advantage against them."

Other students considered how some students benefit from free GAI tools that they would not normally have access to which helps serve as a "private tutor." One student said, "...having free accessibility (with access to a device) could serve to broaden the education of those who would normally have to pay for websites they couldn't afford (for practice problems for example)." However, institutions and faculty must consider the nuances of access and equity, as one participant asked, "...if paid versions perform better, who can access these? Who feels comfortable using these tools for schoolwork?" This theme highlights the harm inequitable access to tools that could further stratify educational outcomes for students based on socioeconomic status. The tensions that arise from uneven use across the higher education population must be surfaced and addressed in institutional policies about the use of GAI.

6.2.2 The need to revisit plagiarism

In general, faculty were more likely to make explicit connections to "plagiarism." For example, "I am most concerned about plagiarism -- presenting another's work as your own." The code for "concerns about plagiarism/cheating" was the most frequently applied after "teaching and learning." Another faculty member wrote, "I see it being used by students to write text reports for them in violation of honor code and ethical standards." Yet, when this survey was distributed, there was no direct mention of GAI in the JMU honor code nor established ethical standards for its use. This lack of guidance may have contributed to reported fears about this technology:

...it's a slippery slope and ... using AI generated writing is no different than plagiarism (confusing ethics if it is allowed). I also don't think undergraduates would use it to support but would instead replace essential critical thinking processes. Also, it creates inequities amongst students when use is inconsistent. Frankly, I'm frustrated and terrified.

The strong negative feelings expressed by this respondent are consistent with DoI theory, which portrays passionate individuals during the preliminary stages of adoption as visionaries and enthusiasts, with hesitance from pragmatists who have not yet been convinced of the innovation's value. In our survey, perhaps because of the unknown broader societal impacts should GAI reach widescale adoption, many early users in academic roles reported passionate negative views about the adoption of the innovation. Students, too, expressed this: "It's wrong to use GAI in any professional capacity. At worst you are stealing and plagiarizing and at best you are taking all human emotion and creativity out of a project."

Indeed, some faculty members asserted that the issue of fairness hinges not on the use of GAI but in the reporting of its use. "It's not terribly different for me from working with a coauthor or speaking with a fellow expert...GAI should be given attribution for what we use of what it generates." Another faculty member wrote, "We just need a citation standard, and the tools should generate some linkable reference material such as the set of questions/commands used and the output." These pragmatic suggestions are in line with GAI's diffusion into the early adopters at the time of the survey's distribution. However, recent efforts to systematize this attribution have faced challenges, indicating that making use of GAI transparent might be easier said than done.

6.3 Ethical consideration #3: Considering who is harmed

Our final themes encapsulate the varied responses that looked beyond the learner, beyond courses at an institution of higher education, and considered the ethics on a broader scale. Several faculty and staff members highlighted ethical considerations and harm related to liberty (e.g., consent and autonomy), rights, authority, and outcomes as they grappled with ownership, authorship, credit, and privacy. Because the LLM that GAI draws from lacks attributions to original writers or creators, it calls into question ownership and credit for what is then created from using GAI. This issue of ownership regarding the content used for training data to develop the LLM was mentioned by several respondents:

... it's unethical to use tools that take from sources often used without permission or credit as the basis for any personal gain such as profit or social gain. It's dishonest and steals work from those who have little to no say in how their effort is used.

One faculty member explicitly considered the economic harm saying, "I'm particularly concerned about the lack of credit/payment to writers/artists/etc. whose work these tools were trained on." Another faculty member echoed this concern for what is also produced by subsequent people using GAI, saying, "I think it unethical to claim credit for its work because we still move through economies of credit and intellectual ownership based on points of origination." Students, too, asked these questions, wondering, "Some ethical considerations for GAI tools are the copyright laws around the content generated, basically who owns what ChatGPT creates?"

6.4 Ethical consideration #4: Determining who is responsible for mitigating harm

Responsibility for harm reduction actions fell into three main camps: university, faculty, or society. Faculty, staff, and students alike noted that the university should play a significant role in developing guidelines for GAI use to mitigate the negative aspects of GAI in teaching and learning described above. However, some noted that faculty must change how they are teaching and adapt GAI into their assignments or conversely, create assignments, policies, and structures that eliminate it from their classroom altogether. Regardless of responsibility, information was desperately needed as one instructor lamented, "GAI is forcing academics to rethink their pedagogy and assignments. Unfortunately, faculty are not receiving the tools or education necessary to really formulate how to alter their methods."

Responsibility concerns regarding the need for legislative and corporate regulations were also cited by several participants with one participant suggesting, "...there should be regular audits conducted to ensure that standards are continually being upheld." There is a clear demand for guidance that has yet to be fully addressed two years after this

survey was conducted. Attempts to create guidelines that do not address the ethical considerations surfaced from these data and situated within established and new ethical frameworks (see Tables 5 and 6) are likely to fall short of providing the support that students, faculty, and staff demanded.

Table 5. Findings situated within established AI core principles and 8KQs

Established AI Core Principles (Jobin et al., 2019)	AI Description (adopted from Laine et al., 2025)	Related 8KQs (JMU, 2018) of higher education participants	Ethical themes from higher education participants in Fall 2023
Justice & Fairness	Considers issues related to LLMs in design, training, and implementation to avoid bias and treat all users equitably	Fairness Outcomes Responsibility Authority Rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Determining how to address inaccuracy and bias • Understanding perceptions of fairness • GAI, equity, and inclusion • Considering who is harmed • Determining who is responsible for mitigating harm
Transparency	Considers issues related to how LLMs work and from where they get their information	Responsibility Rights Authority Outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding perceptions of fairness • Determining how to address accuracy and bias • GAI, equity, and inclusion • Considering who is harmed • Need to address plagiarism
Responsibility	Considers how organizations are accountable for their GAI systems	Responsibility Outcomes Character Authority	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Considering who is harmed • Determining who is responsible for mitigating harm
Privacy	Considers how LLMs risk personal data, security, and copyright	Outcomes Responsibility Liberty Rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Determining who is responsible for mitigating harm
Non-maleficence	Considers the negative uses of GAI that could harm (e.g., spam, cyberattacks etc.) and cybersecurity	Outcomes Responsibility Fairness Authority Rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Determining how to address accuracy and bias • Considering who is harmed • Determining who is responsible for mitigating harm • Need to address plagiarism

Table 6. Findings situated within new GAI ethical principles

Generative AI ethics principles (Laine et al., 2025)	Description (adopted from Laine et al., 2025)	Related 8KQs (JMU, 2018) in ethical considerations of higher education participants	Ethical themes from higher education participants in Fall 2023
Respect for Intellectual Property	Considers issues of copy-right, privacy, freedom and autonomy, ownership, and control	Liberty Rights Authority Outcomes Fairness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need to address plagiarism • Determining who is harmed • Determining who is responsible for mitigating harm
Robustness	Considers issues related to cybersecurity, data leaks, accuracy, current information, and performance.	Fairness Outcomes Responsibility Rights Liberty Authority Rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Determining who is responsible for mitigating harm
Sociocultural responsibility	This considers the social and cultural impacts and consequences such as inequities, digital divides, and cultural representation.	Responsibility Fairness Outcomes Empathy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Determining how to address inaccuracy and bias • Understanding perceptions of fairness • GAI, equity, and inclusion • Need to address plagiarism • Considering who is harmed • Determining who is responsible for mitigating harm
Truthfulness	Issues of accuracy of LLM consumption and content generated, and misinformation.	Fairness Outcomes Responsibility Character Liberty Authority Rights	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Determining how to address inaccuracy and bias • Determining who is responsible for mitigating harm
Recognition of malicious uses	This principle considers issues such as honesty, prejudice, manipulation, toxicity, and the creation of harmful content.	Outcomes Character Responsibility Fairness Empathy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Determining how to address inaccuracy and bias • Understanding perceptions of fairness • Need to address plagiarism

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Determining who is responsible for mitigating harm
			GAI, equity, and inclusion
Human-centric design	de-technology prompt design, human-computer interactions and emotional awareness, and originality.	This considers issues like dependence, interactions and originality.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Considering who is harmed • Determining who is responsible for mitigating harm • Need to address plagiarism
		Outcomes Responsibility Character Empathy Authority Rights	

Our study provides insight on how students, faculty, and staff at one particular institution have thought about GAI and ethics throughout their early mainstream adoption. Although it does not represent the entire university population and therefore has the possibility of having survey non-response bias, we attempted to gather a variety of perspectives in lieu of making large-scale claims. Due to the ever-changing environment of GAI, the findings may not be applicable to other contexts or times; however, they offer a valuable look into what end-users are considering ethically as they begin to experience GAI at a critical time in DoI.

Participants' responses within the themes that were identified reflect the patterns associated with early stages of diffusion processes. Early adopters, who were enthusiastic about the opportunity and experimentation aspects of GAI, contrasted with late adopters (and/or those who are pragmatically inclined), who were uncertain, fearful, or hesitant based upon their perceptions of the ethics surrounding GAI. The differing views among participants exemplify how ethical reasoning can become intertwined with users' perceptions of risk, the degree of advantage perceived in GAI compared to existing technologies, and compatibility with current practices, which are three primary constructs associated with DoI. In essence, participants' ethical assessments of GAI were part of the process by which the innovation was diffusing across the institution.

It should also be noted that participants frequently provided opposing viewpoints regarding GAI, indicating that there is still much ambiguity during the initial stage of diffusion. Participants provided examples such as describing GAI as an effective means to promote equity and provide support to learners with varying abilities, yet concurrently warned that its implementation could widen the gap of inequity and undermine fairness. Additionally, participants viewed GAI as a viable tool for maintaining academic integrity, while viewing it as an unacceptable tool unless implemented in a transparent manner using appropriate skills. Such contradictions indicate that the ethical assessment of GAI will likely be dynamic, and that the consideration of opportunity will need to be balanced against caution.

7. Implications

The findings of this study's participants are still relevant today and will likely be significant for years to come. These findings represent the continued expansion of GAI into higher education and further enhance the growing body of work regarding the ethical implications of GAI, while also addressing several current research gaps (i.e., end-users' ethical issues regarding GAI). By demonstrating that initial ethical concerns may predict future policy requirements, curriculum revisions, and changes in an institution's culture, this study adds to higher education research. As such, the findings of this study are particularly beneficial at the early stages of institutional response to GAI, as the findings highlight when and under what conditions institutions initially develop GAI-related policies, training programs, and governance models. Therefore, institutions like James Madison University—and the broader higher education community—are urged to respond quickly to provide:

- a) institution-wide GAI use policies and guidelines;
- b) clearly defined roles and responsibilities for faculty members to integrate GAI into course content;
- c) comprehensive GAI-ethics training for faculty members and students; and
- d) an equitable understanding of the potential and limitations of GAI.

Through collaboration between faculty, instructional design professionals, students, and industry partners, there is tremendous potential to redefine learning spaces using GAI. In addition, collaborative partnerships have the potential to develop real-world projects and experiential learning opportunities that use GAI to address some of the most pressing challenges and inequalities facing education and society. Developing responsible usage policies is crucial to ensuring that GAI is integrated into academic settings without compromising academic integrity. Academic institutions and instructors must intentionally revise assignment designs and develop new pedagogies that utilize GAI as a tool for facilitating deeper learning rather than as a means of achieving shortcuts to knowledge acquisition. If GAI is utilized responsibly, it has the ability to facilitate both immediate academic success and long-term cognitive and ethical development. Future research studies should investigate how faculty members, staff, and students from diverse backgrounds and disciplines experience GAI over time, including their uses, perceptions, and concerns.

Collectively, these evolving lines of research can significantly contribute to the expanding body of literature on the ethics of GAI, its diffusion throughout higher education, faculty development, curricular innovation, and assessments. Given the rapid rate at which GAI is being adopted in both professional and personal settings, this study provides timely recommendations for policy makers, trainers, and developers of GAI-related products. We present key recommendations (see table 7), supported by the findings of our study, that build upon existing ethical frameworks for AI (Jobin et al., 2019) and GAI (Laine et al., 2025) to inform and support the development of nuanced GAI policies and usage in education.

Table 7. University GAI ethics guidance checklist

-
- Assess the Impact on Student Learning**
 - Acknowledge both potential benefits and risks of GAI for student learning (e.g., quick access to information vs. reduced critical thinking)
 - Encourage research and institutional review of GAI's actual impact on learning outcomes
 - Promote pedagogical strategies that *integrate* GAI to enhance, not replace, student learning and skill development, and provide examples of these strategies in use
 - Address Inaccuracy and Bias**
 - Include training for faculty and students on how to critically evaluate GAI outputs for misinformation and bias (e.g., by analyzing output on topics they have deep personal knowledge and experience with)
 - Promote GAI literacy that includes understanding the sources and limitations of LLM training data
 - Acknowledge societal and political implications of biased information in academic contexts
 - Ensure Fairness and Equity**
 - Recognize GAI's potential for increasing accessibility (e.g., for students with disabilities or multilingual learners) while also monitoring potential inequities
 - Define clear and consistent policies regarding acceptable and unacceptable uses of GAI for coursework
 - Address procedural fairness: how the use of GAI affects grading, participation, and learning equity across diverse learners
-

- Provide institutional support to ensure *equitable access* to GAI tools (e.g., device loans, access to premium versions)
- **Revisit Definitions of Academic Integrity and Plagiarism**
 - Update honor codes and academic integrity policies to explicitly address GAI-generated content
 - Distinguish between various levels of GAI use (e.g., brainstorming vs. full text generation)
 - Develop institutional standards for attribution and citation of GAI-generated content
 - Educate students and faculty on when and how to acknowledge GAI assistance
 - Acknowledge the limitations of GAI detectors/trackers; avoid relying solely on these tools to accuse students of misuse, as they can produce false positives and lack transparency
- **Consider Broader Ethical Impacts**
 - Include guidance on the ethical concerns of authorship and intellectual property related to GAI-generated outputs
 - Encourage transparency in the creation and use of content derived from GAI
 - Address concerns about the economic harm to original creators whose work may have trained the LLMs without consent
- **Clarify Responsibility and Accountability**
 - Clearly define who is responsible for setting and enforcing GAI policies—university leadership, faculty, or external bodies
 - Offer professional development and resources to faculty to adapt pedagogy responsibly
 - Consider forming a task force or advisory board to evaluate and update GAI policy as the technology evolves
 - Advocate for external accountability, including corporate transparency and potential legislative oversight
- **Communication and Ongoing Dialogue**
 - Provide opportunities for ongoing dialogue for students, faculty and staff regarding their experiences and issues with GAI
 - Continuously improve the GAI policy using feedback loops to respond to community needs and emerging technology
 - Develop and maintain easy access to current, easily understood FAQs and other resources about GAI ethics and practices

8. Conclusion

Beginning with the findings of this study, the authors have highlighted the ethical complexity of incorporating generative artificial intelligence (GAI) as an integral part of the higher education system. The study's results reflect many of the emerging ethical issues with GAI that are being discussed in the literature (Schlagwein & Willcocks, 2023; Laine et al., 2025). Most notably, the study has identified two different narratives regarding GAI in higher education. On the one hand, there is tremendous potential for GAI to transform the way that teaching and learning occur as well as the way that administrative work is done. On the other hand, the use of GAI in higher education raises numerous important ethical issues including fairness, access, equity, privacy and critical skill development.

The main contribution of this study is the documentation of the ethical thinking at a very early stage of the development of GAI in higher education. The study provides empirical evidence of how higher education communities think about the potential use of GAI in terms of ethical issues prior to any established norms or policy. As such, this study provides early evidence of how the theories of diffusion of innovation (Rogers, 2003) and contemporary AI ethics (e.g.

Floridi et al., 2018) can be used together to understand how end-users negotiate uncertainty, anticipate risks and develop ethical expectations in real-time. Ultimately, these findings highlight the need for institutions of higher education to clearly articulate the guidelines for the use of GAI and to provide training to educators in the responsible use of GAI. Furthermore, institutions of higher education must begin to adapt their pedagogical approaches to fit the changing technological environment.

Ultimately, as institutions of higher education navigate the new landscape of GAI, they must do so collaboratively. The authors believe that the success of GAI in higher education will depend upon the ability of educators, policymakers and industry stakeholders to collaborate effectively to ensure that GAI is implemented ethically. The authors believe that the insights of this study, which are based on the Diffusion of Innovation theory (Rogers, 2003) and the Eight Key Questions (Linder et al., 2019), provide a roadmap for institutions of higher education to move forward in a manner that balances the desire to innovate with the need to act responsibly. Ultimately, future research should build on the findings of this study by assessing the long-term effects of GAI, by developing best practice models for the inclusion of GAI in higher education settings, and by studying a variety of different types of higher education institutions to ensure that the introduction of GAI in higher education settings does not undermine the educational mission of those institutions but rather enhances them.

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Appendix 1

Faculty and Staff Question:

Artificial Intelligence tools use advanced algorithms to understand and generate responses to questions and statements in a way that is similar to how humans communicate. The tools have been trained on a vast amount of text data and can provide information and answer questions on a wide range of topics. Think of ChatGPT and other chatbots as a computer program that can have a conversation with you.

If you have used a tool like ChatGPT, please share your thoughts on the ethical considerations for use of this tool for teaching and learning.

Student Question:

Artificial Intelligence tools use advanced algorithms to understand and generate responses to questions and statements in a way that is similar to how humans communicate. The tools have been trained on a vast amount of text data and can provide information and answer questions on a wide range of topics. Think of ChatGPT and other chatbots as a computer program that can have a conversation with you.

If you have used a tool like ChatGPT, please share your thoughts on the ethical considerations for use of this tool for learning.

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Data Integrity and Transparency: The data and findings presented are accurate and have not been fabricated, falsified, or inappropriately manipulated. Supporting data can be provided upon request.

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